

Halogenation, Part II. Direct Iodination in Presence of Sodium Nitrite and Fuming Sulphuric Acid.

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In a previous communication Varma and Kulkarni, (this *Journal* page 291) it has been shown that iodine can be introduced directly into the benzene nucleus by means of a mixture of fuming nitric and nitrosulphonic acids and that the presence of a small quantity of glacial acetic acid in addition, increases the yield of the iodo-derivatives to a considerable extent. This investigation has been continued further and it has been found possible to introduce iodine directly into the benzene nucleus in presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid. Ordinary concentrated sulphuric acid may be used instead of the fuming acid, but the yield is smaller. In this case also glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) increases the yield of the iodo-compound. Experiments have been made in order to find the proportions that produce the maximum yield of iodo-benzene and the proportions given in Expt. 5 have been found to give the maximum yield. It is possible to get 11.5 g. of iodo-benzene from 10 g. of benzene which comes to about 70 per cent. of the theory. Some benzene remains unacted upon. Any attempt to convert this remaining benzene into iodo-benzene, by heating for a longer period or by changing the proportions of the reacting materials, results in the formation of poly-iodo-derivatives. The yield of

iodo-benzene obtained by this method is better than that obtained by the methods of Datta and Chatterjee (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 43) and of Varma and Kulkarni (*loc cit*). Moreover, the time taken for the operation is short, the whole can be finished in an hour and a half. Toluene and xylene have also been similarly treated and iodo-toluenes and iodo-xylenes been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the experiments tabulated below, a mixture of sodium nitrite, iodine, the hydro carbon and if necessary, glacial acetic acid is put into a round-bottomed flask, connected with a reflux condenser and heated on the water-bath. Sulphuric acid is then dropped in small quantities at a time. At the end of a specified period, the product is washed first with water then with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with distilled water. The product is then dehydrated by fused calcium chloride and distilled.

Instead of fuming sulphuric acid, a mixture of concentrated and fuming sulphuric acid has been used to find if the yield can be improved but without success (*Vide* Expts. 1 and 14). It is interesting to note that the increase of fuming sulphuric acid beyond a certain limit, keeping the quantities of other ingredients the same, does not increase but decreases the yield of the iodo-compounds. (*Vide* Expt. 10).

The fuming sulphuric acid contained 10 per cent. sulphur trioxide.

Serial No. of Expt.	Benzene in c.c.	Iodine in grams.	Sodium nitrite in grams.	Fuming H ₂ SO ₄ in c.c.	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ in c.c.	Acetic acid in c.c.	Time allowed for reaction in hours.	Yield of iodo-benzene in grams.	Unchanged hydrocarbon in c.c.	Solid residue in grams.	
1	15	12	15	10	10	...	2.5	6.0	7	1	
2	15	12	15	20	3.0	4.5	5	3	
3	15	12	...	20	...	2	3.0	0	12	...	
4	15	10	15	20	...	2	1.25	10.5	4.8	0.3	
5	15	10	15	20	...	2	1.5	11.5	3.7	1.2	
6	15	10	15	...	20	2	1.5	8.8	6	...	
7	15	10	15	20	1.5	7.0	6	...	
8	10	10	15	20	...	2	1.5	7.4	1.3	3.0	
9	15	10	15	15	...	2	1.5	8.7	3	...	
	Toluene										
10	15	10	15	15	...	2	1.0	14	3.8	...	
11	15	10	15	20	...	2	1.0	10	3.4	...	
	<i>m</i> -Xylene										
12	15	10	15	20	...	2	0.8	10.3	2.5	...	
13	15	10	15	...	20	2	0.8	7.5	9.0	...	
14	15	10	15	10	10	2	0.8	8.7	5.0	...	

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